

MOLECULAR ECOLOGY RESOURCES

Supplemental Information for:

Transitioning from environmental genetics to genomics using mitogenome reference databases.

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FIGURE S1

Catostomidae Neighbor-Joining Tree

NJ tree for family Catostomidae created using NAD2 gene extraction. Specimen(s) with species reassignments are highlighted in blue.

FIGURE S2

Centrarchidae, Petromyzontidae, and Ictaluridae Neighbor-Joining Trees

Centrarchidae (top) and Ictaluridae (bottom) NJ trees derived from NAD2 extractions, and Petromyzontidae (middle) NJ tree using concatenated NAD4, NAD5, and NAD6 gene extractions. Specimen(s) with species reassignments are highlighted in blue.

FIGURE S3

Cyprinidae Neighbor-Joining Tree

NJ tree for family Cyprinidae derived from NAD2 extraction. Specimen(s) with species reassignments are highlighted in blue.

FIGURE S4

Cottidae Neighbor-Joining Tree

NJ tree for family Cottidae derived from NAD2 extraction. Specimen(s) with species reassignments are highlighted in blue.

FIGURE S5

Creating a Reference Sequence Database for Monitoring with eDNA

A one-page blueprint designed to provide researchers with the basic steps to follow to create a regional database of full mitogenome sequences for collected target taxa.

BOX S1

Sampling Kit Details

Materials and instructions used to assemble a sampling kit for specimen collection.

Kit Preparation

Contents Per Kit:

1 Extra Large Ziplock Handle Bag
1 Large Sample Bag
1 Small Sample Bag

500mL Nalgene container
2.0mL Nunc Cryotube Labeled

200mL 10% Formalin
1.5mL 95% Ethanol

2 ID Labels
2 Zorb Sheets
1 Pair Individually-wrapped Scissors
1 Set Individually-wrapped Tweezers
1 Pair Individually-wrapped sterile gloves
1 Bleach Wipe
1 Sample Collection Protocol
1 Field Notes Sheet

Instructions:

1. Check that the same ID number is on both ID labels and the field notes sheet.
2. Place 1 ID label in 2.0mL nunc cryotube and 1 ID label in 500mL Nalgene container.
3. Carefully transfer 200mL 10% Formalin into 500mL Nalgene container. Close container tightly without over tightening.
4. Carefully transfer 1.5mL 95% Ethanol into 2.0mL Nunc cryotube. Close tube tightly without over tightening.
5. Put 500mL Nalgene container and 2 Zorb sheets into large sample bag and seal bag tightly.
6. Put 2.0mL Nunc cryotube into small sample bag and seal bag tightly.
7. Place scissors, tweezers, sterile gloves, bleach wipe, sample collection protocol, and field notes sheet into large ziplock handle bag along with both sample bags.

BOX S2

OBGP Sample Collection Protocol

Detailed collection protocol to standardize sampling.

Sample Collection Protocol

A note about permitting and collection: Though fish capture techniques (seine, gill net, angling, shocking, etc.) are beyond the scope of this guide, all specimens must have been obtained legally, typically under a Scientific Taking Permit from the Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife or appropriate state, federal, or international agency.

*** Please read sample collection procedure carefully before collecting fish ***

Note: Do not open 500mL Nalgene container containing Formalin until after tissue sample is collected. Formalin degrades DNA and cannot contact tissues used for genetic analysis.

Sample Collection Procedure:

1. After capturing target fish, ready camera (if available), nunc cryotube, scalpel or biopsy punch, scissors, tweezers, bleach wipe, and gloves.
2. Anesthetize and euthanize fish according to ACUP and IACUC protocols.† If possible, anesthetize/ euthanize fish individually, in a separate container from other fish.
3. Once fish is euthanized, if you have a camera, place fish on its side facing to the left with its left side facing up and photograph fish. After photographing, turn fish over so its right side is facing up.
4. Unwrap and put on sterile gloves. Unwrap scissors. If tools become contaminated at any time wipe thoroughly with bleach wipe to decontaminate. Unwrap tweezers if you decide to use them (They're terrible. Sorry!).
5. Make sure fish is secure and open 2.0mL nunc cryotube. It is helpful to have one person hold the cryotube while another person collects the tissue sample.
6. Get hold of the fish and, using scissors, clip right pelvic fin getting as much tissue as you can. If you are unable to collect 0.5 cm³ of tissue with just the fin clip, use scalpel or biopsy punch (depending on preference) to collect more tissue.

For scalpel: Unwrap scalpel and carefully cut a rectangular piece of tissue from the muscular part of the right side of the fish posterior to its centerline. Try to collect a total of 0.5 cm³.

For biopsy punch: Unwrap biopsy punch and press it firmly into the muscular part of the right side of the fish posterior to its centerline. Rotate the punch and apply pressure until you reach a depth of approximately 0.5 cm. Clasp tissue plug with tweezers and cut out plug with scissors.

7. Place tissue in cryotube, close tube tightly, and place it back in small sample bag.
8. Place the fish into 500mL Nalgene container, close container tightly, and place it in large sample bag.
9. Complete field notes sheet and then place all items, including field notes, back in large, ziplock-handle bag. Please be sure to return all items to ODFW.
10. Contact someone with the OBGP and arrange for tissue sample and voucher specimen to be collected. Thank you for your help with this project! When we're all done, I owe you a beer!

† Specimens should be anesthetized thoroughly before they are euthanized. In addition to meeting the requirements of OSU's Animal Care and Use protocols, such treatment relaxes the muscles of the fish and helps ensure that they are not preserved in a bent condition. The preferred anesthetic for fishes is an aqueous solution of Tricaine mesylate (aka MS-222), buffered with equal molarity of sodium bicarbonate (baking soda). Suggested solution: 400 mg MS-222, 400 mg sodium bicarbonate, and 1 L water.

BOX S3**OBGP Field Notes Sheet**

Metadata collected at the time of specimen sampling.

OBGP FIELD NOTES SHEET**OBGP ID #:** _____ **Locality ID:** _____ [sampling site]**Species:** _____ **Date:** ___/___/___ [month/day/year] **Time:** _____ [24 hour clock]**State/Province:** _____ **County:** _____**Drainage Basin:** _____ **Subbasin:** _____**Description of Locality:** [Describe the sampling site so that someone can readily find the site again using the description]

Photo Taken: Yes No **Datum:** WGS84 or Other: _____ [please specify] **Elevation:** _____ [m]**GPS Model:** _____ **Georeference method:** GPS or Other _____ [please specify]*Please provide 3 separate readings of either UTM's [in meters] or Latitude and Longitude [in decimal degrees e.g 40.446° N 79.982° W]*

Zone	Easting	Northing	Latitude	Longitude
_____	_____	_____	_____	_____
_____	_____	_____	_____	_____
_____	_____	_____	_____	_____

Permit number: _____ **ACUP #:** _____**Collector(s):** _____**Capture Method(s):** _____**Weather:** _____**Substrate** [estimate percents]: Mud ___ Leaf Litter ___ Sand ___ Gravel ___ Rock ___ Other: _____ [please specify]**Water Type** [circle one]: Fresh/Black Fresh/Clear Fresh/White Brackish Salt Other? _____**Water Level** [circle one]: Low Medium High Peak Unknown **Stream Gradient** [circle one]: Flat Slight Moderate High Unknown**Stream Width:** estimate: <2 m 2-5 m 5-10 m 10-20 m 20-50 m 50-100 m >100 m or exact measurement _____ [m]**Optional Measurements:****Depth of Capture:** Min _____ [m] Max _____ [m] **Distance of Capture from Shore:** Min _____ [m] Max _____ [m]**Temperature:** Air _____ °C Water _____ °C **Salinity:** _____ [specify units] **Turbidity:** Secchi _____ [m]**Water Velocity:** _____ [m/sec] **Water: pH** _____ **Conductivity** _____ [μS/cm] **O₂** _____ [mg/L]**Notes:**